

ARCHITECTURE AND PROPERTIES OF STOCHASTIC FOAM MODELS

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ABSTRACT

Recent results from numerical analysis of the microstructure and constitutive properties of foams are presented and relations between these properties and various topological differences in the cellular architecture are illustrated and discussed. The focus is on closed cell foams but parts of the work concern effects of distribution of solid between the cell walls and edges, which then also include open cell foams.

The study is based on a modelling scheme where Voronoi partitioning is conducted, based on seed point distributions coming from random packings of hard spheres. The models are then brought to surface energy equilibrium through use of the Surface Evolver software. Sphere packing, partitioning of space and relaxation of the cellular models are conducted on periodic representative volume elements (RVE), typically containing in the order of 100 cells. Finite element models of the foam architecture is then performed with various sets of periodic boundary conditions in order to study the model topology, convergence rates and extract representative constitutive properties for the studied cases.

The results are compared with other simulation results from the literature, experimental data and measurements made from SEM and CT micrographs. Some differences between evaluations of 2D and 3D representations of the foam materials are also illustrated and discussed.

Aspects of the generation of the models are illustrated, indicating that some model results are virtually unaffected by most of the model details while other results depend strongly on the input parameters and differences between modelling techniques.

Some references are also made to classical foam property estimates coming from dimension analysis of idealised foam structures where the relatively simplistic models in many cases provide surprisingly good estimates of the mechanical properties of the foam materials. There are however also some significant differences that are highlighted and explained in the presentation.

1 INTRODUCTION

Foams constitute an interesting class of materials with several unique properties making them useful in a wide range of applications. Common for all foams is that they are inhomogeneous but since most other general statements about their characteristics call for further distinction the class of materials is further split into sub-classes before continuing. The foams of primary interest in this paper are solid, implying that e.g. concepts like stiffness are meaningful for their characterisation.

Foams are in general three-dimensional (3D) structures and when it comes to modelling they need to be considered accordingly. Two-dimensional (2D) models or projections of foams could at best provide some principal estimates of the foam properties but unless knowledge about their 3D character is built into the models they could merely represent 3D extrusions of the 2D projections they represent.

We here also consider foams to be amorphous although there exist some regular foam structures as well. The latter are relatively easy to build and analyse, which have made them popular in modelling work, but they are typically also different from true foams in the sense that they are monodisperse, i.e. have cells with equal size, might lack isotropy and have different connectivity or show other

geometrical relations [1-3] than real amorphous foam materials. The regular tetrakaidecahedron, known as the Kelvin cell [4] is however convenient and meaningful to use as a reference since it, stemming from body-centred cubic arrangements of (equi-sized) spheres, is the single cell able to fill space that has the lowest surface area per cell volume.

The maybe most significant property of a foam material is its relative density, i.e. the ratio between the density of the foam and that of its solid raw material. We here focus on foams with relative densities in the range 0.03-0.3 but as will be discussed later some idealisations of the foam models might not be fully justified for the higher relative densities.

For the preceding discussion of foam properties we refer to Fig. 1 where a typical cell polyhedron is illustrated and its characteristic constituents; faces, edges and vertices; are illustrated.

Figure 1: A schematic irregular foam cell, here in the shape of a triskaidecahedron.

Another feature of foam materials is their distribution of solid material. In real foam materials the cell wall thickness is usually quite uniform, although it might differ between individual faces. However, effects related to the surface tension tend to draw the raw material towards the edges of the faces while the foam is still in a liquid phase, making the cell walls thicker in the vicinity of the edges, where the edges themselves usually have tricuspid cross sections. The structure of a real, Rohacell polymethacrylimide (PMI), foam material is presented in the SEM image in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: A SEM image of a real foam material (Rohacell PMI, IG51)

A slightly simplified but yet convenient definition of the distribution of solid is thus to distinguish between the fraction of raw material f_e belonging to the edges and f_w belonging to the face walls, with the obvious ambiguity it implies.

2 METHOD

In the presented work foam models are built from Voronoi spatial partitioning using the centres of randomly packed hard spheres as nuclei for the cell origins. The spheres are packed in RVEs constituting control volumes that typically contain in the order of 100 cells. The volume of the i :th cell is defined by

$$V_i = \{ \bar{x} = \Omega \mid \|x - x_i\| \leq \|x - x_j\|, i \neq j \} \quad (1)$$

i.e. by all points in the domain being closer to the i :th nucleus than to any other nucleus (j) within the domain. It was shown in previous work [5] that both statistical measures of geometrical features and elastic constants extracted from the models converge for as little as 100 cells in the type of models used in this study.

The distances in eq. (1) are defined in cyclic Euclidian space making both the sphere packings and the Voronoi partitions periodic by requiring cyclic repetition over the RVE boundaries. If the spheres are densely packed, but below the random closed packed (RCP) limit, the cells become spheroid with close to uniform cell size. As mentioned above foams with uniform cell size are referred to as monodisperse. Correspondingly, foams with varying cell size are called polydisperse. The polydispersity is here conveniently defined as the coefficient of variation of the cell volume, i.e. as

$$cv(V) = \frac{\sigma_V}{\bar{V}} \quad (2)$$

where σ_V and \bar{V} are the standard deviation and mean value of the cell volume, respectively.

The cells in models coming from Voronoi partitioning are mathematically convex polyhedra with plane faces, which fill space completely. The faces meet at edges and the edges meet at vertices (see Fig. 1) so that they satisfy Plateau's laws, stipulating that three cells (three faces) are interconnected along each internal edge and four cells (four edges) share each internal vertex.

The preceding sphere packing generates Voronoi nuclei that are randomly but yet relatively evenly distributed, with a distance between two neighbouring nuclei typically in the range of 1-1.5 sphere diameters for reasonably densely packed spheres. An illustration of a periodic RVE containing 64 densely packed spheres is presented in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: An RVE containing densely packed spheres where the centre points define cell nuclei for Voronoi spatial partitioning.

If the spheres are more sparsely packed the resulting Voronoi partitioning tends to generate cells that are less spheroid, thus appearing unnatural to the eye and, in more quantitative measures, showing a higher face surface to cell volume ratio. In real liquid foams, surface tension acts to equilibrate such energetic frustration by rearrangement into more spheroid cells.

Voronoi foam models are also known to contain relatively high fractions of small cell faces and edges [3,6]. Not only are such features unnatural in the sense that they are absent in real foams but they also generate a lot of finite element (FE) modelling challenges since they require high mesh

refinement, which in turn drives the computing costs. Researchers working with Voronoi foam models use various methods to remove tiny faces and edges from their models but doing that is generally associated with manipulations of the foam architecture which are often neither performed stochastically nor based on physical principles unless very sophisticated methods are used. The details of such procedures are also often omitted when the work is presented.

In the present work the software Surface Evolver [7] is used to bring the Voronoi models to surface energy equilibrium, using an approach similar to that of Kraynik et al. e.g. [3,8]. The software changes the surface size of the cell faces and triggers topology transitions allowing faces to vanish or materialize in order to comply with Plateau's laws as part of the transitions. The procedure can start from relatively crude Voronoi partitions, since it cleans out un-natural features of the cellular structure and make the cells more spheroid, driven by minimisation of surface area.

As part of minimizing the cell face area Surface evolver also cleans out the small faces and edges found in Voronoi foams, since they don't comply with low total surface area. In addition Surface Evolver introduces equiangular intersections of the faces along mutual edges, and of the edges at mutual vertices, which inherently also introduces cell wall and edge curvatures.

In the presented work some sparse random packings of spheres are used as a means to reach higher polydispersity in foam models. Subsequent energetic relaxation with Surface evolver then reshapes the cells of the foams, while conserving their volume, so that they become spheroid in spite of the crude features of their Voronoi precursors.

However, two limitations turn out: There seems to be a limit to how polydisperse the foams can be made through Voronoi partitioning and for the most polydisperse cases the cells become so ill-conditioned that it is difficult to run the models through Surface Evolver. The code iteratively executes series of cell face size changes and topology transitions and if the starting conditions are too poor it is very cumbersome to find a stable route to equilibrium due to the multitude of very small steps that are required.

An alternative way to reach more disperse populations of cell sizes in foam models is to use Laguerre partitioning which is a weighted Voronoi procedure. Several researchers have used that approach, e.g. [9-11], but then not converted the Laguerre models to equilibrium models. It was shown by the authors that conversion to equilibrium alters the microstructure of Voronoi foams [12] and it is reasonable to assume that the same would be true also for Laguerre models.

The models generated in this work are analysed with the finite elements (FE) using ABAQUS and it is then possible to vary the distribution of solid material between the cell faces and edges by modelling the faces with shell elements and the edges with beams and then vary the ratio between the thicknesses of the two cell constituents. The distribution of solid ϕ is defined as the fraction of material in the cell edges, in accordance with the definitions by Gibson and Ashby [13] and $\phi = 1$ then corresponds to an open cell foam without any cell walls.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In the following a selection of results from the work with the equilibrium foam models is presented to provide an overview of some of the important findings. Some of the results were already published while others in the writing moment are in the process of becoming so.

3.1 Topology differences between Voronoi and equilibrium foams

As mentioned above Voronoi models contain small features (cell faces and edges) that are not found in real structural foams. Fig. 4 shows results from previous work by the authors [6] where edge length distributions from two types of Voronoi seed generation procedures, i.e. random sequential adsorption (RSA) and random close packing (RCP) of spheres, are compared for models containing either 50 or 150 cells. The very same models are then brought to equilibrium (relaxed) using Surface Evolver, and new sets of models; (RSA-R) and (RCP-R) are then obtained. The figure shows the fraction of edges in various length spans where the edge lengths have been normalised with the cubic root of the average cell volume.

Figure 4: Occurrence of normalized edge lengths l in Voronoi foam models (RSA and RCP) and corresponding equilibrium models (RSA-R and RCP-R), containing 50 or 150 cells.

As seen in Fig. 4 the Voronoi models contain high fractions of short edges, which the equilibrium models do not. It is also seen that the two types of Voronoi models show different distributions of edge lengths while the distributions from the corresponding equilibrium models show much better mutual agreement. Finally all distributions are relatively insensitive to the number of cells in the models in the range 50-150 cells. Similar results were found for the cell face areas.

3.2 Effects of sphere packing on the polydispersity and cell topology

The polydispersity possible to obtain from Voronoi partitioning based on spheres at various level of packing was found to be limited to $cv(V)$ in the order of 0.5. The equilibrium models were even more limited in polydispersity due to the computing challenges in Surface Evolver mentioned above. It was however clear that there were topological differences between Voronoi models at different polydispersities while the equilibrium models showed very little variation over the available range of cell size distributions.

The trend is clearly seen in Fig. 5 where the average number of faces per cell for various levels of polydispersity is presented for a large group of models. Data reported in the literature for Kelvin foam [4] and some real foam materials [2,14,15] are also presented in the figure, apparently being in better agreement with the results from the equilibrium models than from the Voronoi models.

Figure 5: Average number of faces per cell for Voronoi models (Vor.), equilibrium models (Rel.) the Kelvin cell and various real foam materials from the literature.

There is a certain scatter between the results from the Voronoi models, which is also greater for models containing 50 cells than models containing 150 cells, but the overall trend is very consistent. The equilibrium models show results with considerably lower scatter and also clearly indicate that the average number of faces per cell is constant in the studied range of cell size dispersity.

3.4 Influence from relative density and distribution of solid on constitutive properties of foams

Gibson and Ashby suggested what must now be considered as classical relations for the elastic properties of foams based on dimensional analysis of idealised cell structures [13], stating e.g. that

$$\frac{E^*}{E_s} = C_1 \phi^2 \left(\frac{\rho^*}{\rho_s} \right)^2 + C_2 (1 - \phi) \frac{\rho^*}{\rho_s} \quad (3)$$

where E and ρ represent the elastic modulus and the density of the foam (*) and the solid raw material (s), respectively, and C_1 and C_2 are coefficients representing a particular foam architecture.

In Fig. 6 the results from a parametric study using the equilibrium models are presented. The relative density and the distribution of solid were varied and 10 models were run for each combination of parameters. The coefficients C_1 and C_2 in eq. 3 were then determined by making a least square fit to the numerical results.

Figure 6: Elastic modulus versus relative density for various distributions of solid, where the markers represent model data and the lines provide the best fit to eq. (3).

The scatter between the results from the 10 models is indicated by error bars but it is so small that it is barely visible in the figure. The agreement with eq. (3) is reasonably good but far from perfect, which is believed to be due to the idealisations made to arrive at eq. (3). It is assumed that the deformation of the foam is dominated by stretching of cell walls and bending of cell edges but since other deformation mechanisms might also affect the stiffness an attempt was made to generalize the relation in eq. (3).

The relations suggested by Gibson and Ashby were thus reformulated to allow for inclusion of other deformation mechanisms that might also come into play. That was done by reformulation according to

$$\frac{E^*}{E_s} = f(\phi) \left(\frac{\rho^*}{\rho_s} \right)^2 + g(\phi) \frac{\rho^*}{\rho_s} \quad (4)$$

where $f(\phi)$ is a general 2nd order polynomial and $g(\phi)$ is a general 1st order polynomial, with coefficients that were again derived from least square fits to the numerical results. The outcome is presented in Fig. 7, showing that the generalised expression in eq. (4) provides a much better

agreement with the results from the numerical simulations.

Figure 7: Elastic modulus versus relative density for various distributions of solid, where the markers represent model data and the lines provide the best fit to eq. (4).

3.3 Effect of polydispersity on the stiffness of foams

In Fig. 8 more results from the equilibrium models are presented indicating that the elastic modulus of foam materials is independent of the polydispersity in the investigated range. The relative density is 0.1 in the presented models and the distribution of solid is That is an interesting result since it differs from what was recently reported in another study based on Laguerre foam models [11]. Further to the discussion the result in this study seems to be in agreement with not yet published results from open cell equilibrium foams [16].

Figure 8: Elastic modulus versus polydispersity for equilibrium foam models.

4 CONCLUSIONS

A methodology for systematic numerical studies of foam materials is presented. It has been developed and used to study how both topological measures and elastic properties of foams vary with different model parameters.

It is shown that models that are brought to surface energy equilibrium provide results in better agreement with data from real foams and provide different predictions of properties than obtained from Voronoi models.

It is found that topological features like the average number of faces per cell varies with the cell size dispersity for Voronoi models but not for equilibrium models.

Even more interestingly the equilibrium models also suggest that the stiffness of the foam materials is independent of cell size dispersity.

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